

Passive Exoskeletons and Human Digital Twins: An Integrated Perspective for Ergonomic Improvement

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Abstract: There has been a growing interest in the development of innovative technologies to improve health and human performance in work environments. Wearable devices such as exoskeletons are adopted in industries to reduce the risk of musculoskeletal injuries for workers. Computational models that replicate physical and functional characteristics of real individuals, like digital human twins, are increasingly used to simulate and predict human performance in different scenarios. The integration of these two technologies emerges as a promising approach for ergonomic monitoring and predictive analysis. This study aimed to discuss the application of passive exoskeletons and the development of digital human twins for monitoring and predictive analysis related to ergonomic conditions. Therefore, this article provides a comprehensive review of the literature on passive exoskeletons, focusing on potential studies that allow integration with digital human twins, as well as a critical and scientific analysis by the authors. Thus, a mapping and data collection analyses demonstrate a variety of applications of exoskeletons, focusing on diversity and potential for integration with digital twins technology. In addition to the plurality of contexts in which these technologies are applied, the importance of a multidisciplinary approach to fully understand their effects and benefits is also highlighted. It was possible to provide valuable insights for researchers, industry professionals, as well as policymakers interested in promoting the use of these technologies to improve working conditions and the well-being of workers.

Keywords: Ergonomic monitoring; Occupational health; Wearable technologies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Technologies disseminated by the 4th Industrial Revolution, such as artificial intelligence, Internet of Things, Digital Twins and robotics, make it feasible for interaction and collaboration between humans and intelligent machines in automated work environments. However, even with technological advancements and increasingly complex and automated systems, humans remain a key component for industrial manufacturing systems. Furthermore, there are still manual and repetitive activities that are excessively performed by employees, resulting in physical strain in their daily operations (Simon; Alemi; Asbeck, 2021).

Human behavior is often disregarded in the design of operational procedures and automated systems. In some specific situations, such as ergonomic analysis, humans are treated as static elements, with unchangeable behavior limited to physical interactions, disregarding emotional and physiological factors (Montini et al. 2021). Currently, 15% of the world population suffers from some disability, affecting the capacity for total or partial self-sufficiency regarding the performance of daily activities (Huamanchahua et al. 2021).

Prolonged or repetitive work in incorrect postures is a known risk factor for the development of lower back disorders (Ulrey and Fathallah, 2013). Among occupational health

problems, low back pain (lumbar injuries) is one of the major health complications causing widespread personal suffering; the incidence of back disorders is higher especially in employees working in areas such as construction, transportation, storage, healthcare, automotive, which require greater physical movement (Baltrusch et al. 2018; Ko et al. 2018). In pursuit of better working conditions, technologies such as exoskeletons and digital human twins can be considered to dynamically monitor ergonomic conditions.

Exoskeletons refer to the purpose of protecting and supporting the human body. In technological terms, they are mechanical structures attached to the user's body, aiming to provide benefits such as reducing physical effort and amplifying the user's strength (Du Plessis; Djouani; Oosthuizen, 2021; Huamanchahua et al. 2021). Exoskeletons are categorized into two groups of wearable machines: active, where the exoskeleton with power source and actuators perform the user's movement; and passive, where the user's movement is assisted by the exoskeleton without actuators or internal power source. Thus, they are capable of meeting the needs of both the upper and lower limbs of humans, potentially offering a wide variety of configurations aiming for optimal performance (Baltrusch et al., 2018; Lecturer, 2021). Machine designs with exoskeletons are ways to obtain productive systems from the perspective of employee needs,

therefore emerging as a promising technology to reduce physical efforts of employees (Ippolito; Constantinescu; Rusu, 2020; European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, 2020; Constantinescu et al. 2019).

A recurring problem in the implementation of wearable technologies, such as exoskeletons, relates to user adaptation. The difficulty of adaptation is directly related to the complexity of the work environment, whether in operational safety or in proving the benefits of using exoskeletons. In this sense, there are gaps to be explored regarding the integration of simulation technologies, such as digital twins, with exoskeletons.

In this panorama, the term Human Digital Twin refers to a technological solution to facilitate the integration of the worker with the environment of Industry 4.0 (Sparrow et al. 2019). Digital twins are virtual replicas of a physical entity that establish bidirectional real-time communication between the physical and the virtual, allowing simulations, optimizations with artificial intelligence, and decision-making support (Lim; Zheng; Chen, 2020). In the case of humans, data is collected in real-time through wearable devices and other sensors for the development of a personalized digital model. Digital factories should include realistic models of humans to promote a production system that complements human capabilities. Technologies like these aim not only at optimizing production performance but also at caring for the well-being, mental health, and skills of employees (Montini et al. 2021).

Despite the existence of intelligent, decentralized, and interoperable manufacturing systems, humans continue to be a relevant element in maintaining factory operations with the expected performance. Aspects related to health and safety should be considered as an investment, since the well-being of the employee directly influences their productivity (Kim et al. 2022). Wearable devices applied to professional activities are classified into four categories: monitoring, support, training, and tracking (Sun et al. 2020).

The integration of exoskeletons and human digital twins involves challenges such as the accuracy of body and worker movement modeling, the proper calibration of efforts on the human body before and during the use of the wearable device. Additionally, issues related to connectivity and sensing must be evaluated according to the application, aiming for the acquisition of precise data and interoperability between the physical and virtual. Uncertainties regarding the risks involved in the prolonged use of exoskeletons and user acceptability are some of the challenges to overcome before the widespread use of these devices (European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, 2020).

This work aims to discuss the application of passive exoskeletons and the development of human digital twins for monitoring and predictive analysis related to ergonomic conditions. It contributes to identifying the challenges and limitations related to the implementation of passive exoskeletons and human digital twins for improving work ergonomics, as well as highlighting the potential benefits of these technologies.

This article is organized as follows: in section 2, the description of the systems is presented; in section 3, the analyses and discussion are described; in section 4, the results and perspectives are presented. The article concludes with the conclusions in section 5.

2. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Passive exoskeletons are composed of mechanical structures, typically lightweight and with considerable strength. Baltrusch et al. (2018) describes passive exoskeletons for the trunk and lower limbs as devices that are worn around the waist, front part of the chest, thighs, and posterior at pelvis level, usually with the aid of belts, pads, rigid and flexible elements. Other configurations feature carbon fiber beams, typically installed in areas such as the back and legs, providing restoring force for returning to the body's position (Simon; Alemi; Asbeck, 2021). The operation of the passive exoskeleton is based on a combination of mechanical and biomechanical principles to provide ergonomic assistance. The joints and mechanisms involved are designed to mimic the natural movements of the body, allowing freedom of movement for users.

In an engineering context, the use of advanced 3D modeling techniques plays a fundamental role in the development of ergonomic structures adapted to users. Mastery of these tools is crucial for the design of components capable of efficiently distributing loads and mitigating physical efforts during movements. Regarding control, systems that use integrated sensors are able to provide feedback, allowing dynamic adjustments in the support offered according to the individual needs of the user. Fig. 1 presents examples of exoskeletons applied in an ergonomic setting.

Fig. 1: (A) lumbar region support (Alemi et al. 2019); (B) head and neck support (Garosi et al. 2022); (C) reduction of physical effort in upper limbs and improvement of posture (De Bock et al. 2023); (D) Shoulder support (Dalbøge et al. 2024).

Human digital twins represent detailed virtual models of workers, employed for simulation, optimization, and decision support in industrial environments, simplifying the integration of workers into high-technology environments, such as those aligned with the Industry 4.0 paradigm (Sparrow et al. 2019). The operation of digital twins is based on the continuous collection of real-time data through wearable devices and mainly through portable sensors.

From the engineering and control perspective, the recorded samples are subjected to data analysis algorithms and computational modeling, which are employed in the creation and updating of digital models of workers. These data include ergonomic information about posture, movements, activities, and even physiological signals of workers. These models are elaborated from unique biometric and biomechanical data of each worker, enabling an accurate and personalized representation of physical and behavioral characteristics, and can be integrated into digital models of exoskeletons (Constantinescu et al. 2019).

3. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

For this study, studies describing the design, functioning, and applications of passive exoskeletons in ergonomic contexts were examined, along with their contributions to advancing the field. This selection process resulted in identifying a final set of 9 articles, which were included in the literature review and served as the basis for the analysis and synthesis of the data presented in this study. After selecting the articles, relevant data were extracted and organized as described in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of studies by areas of the human body

Region	Author	Year
Torso	Bosch et al.	2016
Head and neck	Garosi et al.	2022
Shoulders	Dalbøge et al.	2024
Arms	De Bock et al.	2023
Lumbar	Alemi et al.	2019
Ankle	Pardoel e Doumit.	2019

The data analysis provided an in-depth understanding of the current state of research related to this topic and served as a theoretical basis for discussing the results and conclusions of this study, as well as revealing insights highlighting both trends and gaps in the existing literature. Additionally, the results revealed a variety of applications and relevant approaches for the integration between passive exoskeletons and human digital twins. The analyzed studies addressed a wide range of applications of passive exoskeletons for industrial sectors, including manufacturing, healthcare, logistics, and construction, demonstrating the diversity of contexts in which this technology is currently being explored.

Through the analysis of the literature, for the regions of the human body where passive exoskeleton applications are focused, electronic components such as resistive force sensors, luminosity, humidity, atmospheric pressure,

accelerometers, and even load cells, to gauge body overloads, are relevant for the integration of human digital twin technology, proving pertinent for obtaining real-time monitoring of the physical conditions of workers and the work environment in which they operate.

To ergonomically assess work, some techniques are adopted such as postural evaluation, which studies the postures adopted at work, and biomechanical assessment, which investigates the efforts on the joints of employees (De Lima and De Oliveira, 2019). Technological advancements together with policies aimed at preserving human integrity tend to increasingly improve working conditions for employees. As pointed out by authors Bosch et al. (2016), with the progression of these developments, other potentially preventive strategies for manual, strenuous, and repetitive activities emerge, whether through the digitization of operations or wearable technologies. Thus, ergonomic problems such as work-related musculoskeletal disorders resulting from excessive manual work, considered as occupational injuries, are being prevented, thus offering short and long-term well-being to workers (Simon; Alemi; Asbeck, 2021; Alemi et al. 2019).

As observed in the literature review on the need to implement solutions that improve work ergonomics. The repetitiveness of movements, which are inevitably present in manual labor in less automated sectors such as construction, automotive, military, social service activities, as well as in healthcare, haunt employees with the risk of developing problems that incapacitate them from performing their job functions (Garosi et al. 2022; So et al. 2020). In this regard, about 50% of surgeons fear that their pain may lead to retirement (Tetteh; Hallbeck; Mirka, 2022). In the industrial sector, shoulder disorders are occurring in more than 50% of employees currently (De Bock et al. 2023). In the last two decades, the prevalence of chronic neck pain has increased significantly from 20% to 34% (Garosi et al. 2022).

It is essential to establish and implement an effective system of monitoring and ergonomic assistance, especially in scenarios characterized by the recurrence of prolonged work operations and incorrect postures, such as in social service activities (Simon; Alemi; Asbeck, 2021; Ulrey and Fathallah, 2013). In addition to studies with passive exoskeletons that have proven to be relevant for preventing occupational diseases, this approach also facilitates the adaptation of employees to more dynamic work environments (Sparrow et al. 2019).

The application of passive exoskeletons and digital twins in less technological work environments proves beneficial, serving as an alternative means for preventing occupational diseases. In these scenarios, these wearable devices are framed within contexts that involve not only support but also monitoring and tracking (Sun et al. 2020). The adoption of these technologies contributes to promoting the health and safety of employees. Thus, investing in the health and safety of workers is also an investment in the company's productivity (Kim et al. 2022).

From the perspective of integrating technologies to improve interaction between exoskeletons and users, the use of these wearable technologies as a technological solution to mitigate the impacts of repetitive activities is still in its early stages in operational settings. There are cultural barriers, technical limitations, and uncertainties related to medical issues that hinder widespread implementation. Thus, utilizing simulation resources such as digital twins, for example, may be a way to mitigate these risks and bring more safety to users.

The combination of digital twins and exoskeletons is crucial at two stages. Initially, digital modeling of human movements during tasks allows for the accurate identification of the most stressed and demanded body parts. In a second stage, after selecting the exoskeleton, it is possible to couple the digital model of the device and conduct a digital validation of the new ergonomic conditions through simulations before the final introduction of the new tool into the work environment (Ippolito; Constantinescu; Rusu, 2020).

Depending on the complexity of the application, off-the-shelf software will not be sufficient to meet the demands, requiring custom development. Limitations such as the automatic modification of ergonomic parameters of the human after the integration of the exoskeleton and involved loads will necessitate manual adjustments regarding the new values of tensions and efforts on the human body provided by the equipment (Constantinescu et al., 2019).

Simulations of ergonomic conditions for the hybrid worker can provide positive expectations to leverage the use of wearable technologies. Once the software allows digitally comparing the performance of a worker using different exoskeleton models, it will be possible to confirm which configuration offers the best ergonomic conditions or even prove that there are no significant improvements. Authors Ippolito; Constantinescu; Rusu, (2020) emphasize that, for a realistic simulation of the hybrid worker's performance, it is important to associate it with a digital model of the work environment as close to reality as possible, considering layout, machinery, and operational procedures.

It is expected that in the factories of the future, machines and humans will be equipped with technological communication and data processing resources, forming an interconnected ecosystem of mutual cooperation, called human cyber-physical systems (H-CPS). Within this context emerges a new class of worker, the Operator 4.0, aimed at enhancing the interaction between machines and humans using technologies spread by the 4th Industrial Revolution. Authors Romero et al. (2016) explain that Operator 4.0 consists of a new philosophy of design and engineering for adaptive production systems, where the focus is on treating automation as an additional improvement of the physical, sensory, and cognitive capabilities of the human being.

The benefits of using digital twins of humans in validating wearable technologies can be substantial. However, the level of detail of the assets involved in simulations and real-time synchronization of results may require customized software, robust computational infrastructure, and specialized

professionals from different areas, which can delay the maturity of these technologies. Literature analysis has revealed not only significant advancements achieved so far but also knowledge gaps that persist and need to be addressed in future research.

4. RESULTS AND PERSPECTIVES

Currently, the development of an exoskeleton prototype is in the phase of measurements and clinical tests in humans. This research has proceeded with the aim of developing a passive exoskeleton for the lumbar region with the purpose of reducing physical effort and comparing the effects on repetitive manual activities. The exoskeleton in Fig. 2 was designed to provide ergonomic assistance precisely in social service activities, justified by the need to reduce physical efforts due to the excess of manual and repetitive actions to which workers are subjected. Thus, it was constructed according to criteria such as: ability to generate a moment of extension when bending forward; store and release elastic energy during movement (Koopman et al. 2019).

Fig. 2: (A) exoskeleton prototype. (B) Trapezius and waist connection for support. Provides 4 adjustment points to the body, 1 in the waist area and 3 in the chest.

This exoskeleton was 3D printed with PLA material, taking a total time of 45 hours and 18 minutes, with a consumption of 571g of material to assemble the 14 pieces. In this system, there are two 30 cm latex tubes installed on the inner side, connecting all the parts of the exoskeleton. The operation occurs through a variable force, with the Elastic Force depending on the displacement. When the exoskeleton is reducing the physical effort exerted by the user, the system is storing energy to assist in returning to the posture.

After obtaining the prototype, an experimental protocol was developed to submit 8 volunteers to two different activities, performed with and without the exoskeleton, such as: I) picking up and lifting a 1kg object from the ground; and II) repeating the previous activity at a different baseline level. Thus, 10 continuous repetitions were assigned to both activities with a 1 min rest interval, based on the literature (Bosch et al. 2016). After completing each action with and without the exoskeleton, a 30 min rest was provided. During recruitment, profiles without previously diagnosed spinal injuries and without comorbidities were admitted. Additionally, volunteers with mobility limitations or who

experienced pain during the experiment had their participation interrupted and were excluded without reintegration, as part of the exclusion criteria.

During the execution of the assigned tasks, each volunteer's heart rate was monitored and recorded under both conditions. Data collection was conducted using a digital oximeter placed on the volunteers' index finger. To evaluate the relationship between the use of the exoskeleton and the volunteers' heart rate, the Pearson Correlation test was applied. This statistical analysis aimed to determine the strength and direction of the association between the two variables, for comparison of the results.

Table 2 describes the average beats per minute (%bpm) results with the exoskeleton (With Exo) and without the exoskeleton (No Exo). Table 3 presents the analysis of data correction.

Table 2: Heart Rate of the Volunteers

Id	Activity I		Activity II	
	With Exo	No Exo	With Exo	No Exo
v1	99	109	92	99
v2	104	106	94	98
v3	101	104	97	98
v4	103	110	100	107
v5	97	99	97	98
v6	98	103	98	98
v7	93	96	96	98
v8	91	93	94	98

Table 3: Analysis of Heart Rate Data

Id	Activity I	Activity II
v1	0.95	0.80
v2	0.84	0.92
v3	0.95	0.96
v4	0.95	0.87
v5	0.94	0.93
v6	0.92	0.74
v7	0.93	0.92
v8	0.90	0.88

The data analysis revealed a strong positive correlation in all cases. These results suggest high consistency in the effects of the exoskeleton in reducing aerobic effort during the manual activity. The strong correlation confirms that the observed variations in heart rate are directly associated with the use of the exoskeleton, reinforcing the effectiveness of the device in reducing exertion. The lowest value found 0.74, although still within a range considered strong, suggests that there may be individual variations in response to the use of the exoskeleton.

The positive effect observed in the tests is evidenced by the %bpm data, which are lower when performing activities with the presence of the exoskeleton. It is understood that the volunteers exerted less muscle stress when wearing the exoskeleton, as moving fewer muscles requires less oxygen to perform the tasks, thus saving physical effort. The

volunteers did not experience rejection of the exoskeleton garment during the applied tests, nor were there complaints of pain, pressure points, or any other discomfort in the lumbar region.

The next steps involve integrating human digital twins with the developed exoskeleton and testing in conditions more representative of exhaustion in representative long-term work (a work shift, for example). In terms of instrumentation aimed at analyzing ergonomic conditions, sensors such as inclinometers can contribute to quantifying incorrect positions; resistive force sensors can differentiate loads in specific regions of the body; accelerometers and gyroscopes can reveal the speed of movements performed. In this sense, sensors such as distance sensors, obstacle sensors, light sensors, and temperature sensors can be embedded to analyze working conditions. This increases expectations for creating a compatible digital human model for real-time monitoring of employees' ergonomic conditions during their work shifts.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, the existing literature on passive exoskeletons was examined, and the integration with human digital twin technology was discussed, highlighting the applications, challenges, and opportunities associated with these innovative technologies. Additionally, a prototype exoskeleton was presented to aid workers, which was tested in a social service activity with the aim of preventing occupational diseases such as low back pain and improving work performance. The positive effect of the exoskeleton is evidenced by the decrease in heart rate. Statistically, the data continue to support the effectiveness of the device in reducing physical effort, although there are variations that may be attributed to individual factors or the nature of the activity.

The integration of passive exoskeletons and human digital twins represents a promising research area, given its potential to transform the approach to ergonomics in companies and the monitoring of working conditions. This fills gaps observed in the literature, such as the need for more robust studies to investigate the long-term effects of using these technologies, as well as issues related to user acceptance and native system integration.

Therefore, fully understanding the challenges and opportunities associated with the integration of passive exoskeletons and human digital twins will require a multidisciplinary and collaborative approach involving researchers, industry professionals, policymakers, and workers. In this sense, future research related to the integration of these technologies can further advance our understanding and application of these emerging technologies, to promote safer, healthier, and more productive work environments.

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